

Abstract

Migration conveys many benefits to species, ecosystems, and people but relies upon connected landscapes. Anthropogenic development can present barriers for migrants, but many barriers are semi-permeable, allowing unhindered or delayed passage. We used a modified version of the Barrier Behavior Analysis (BaBA) to investigate seasonal movement responses to five roads in northwestern Alaska by adult female Western Arctic Herd caribou (*Rangifer tarandus*) from 2009–2024. Our analyses revealed some altered movement in response to all focal roads. We found that the roads were semi-permeable barriers to movement, with altered behaviors including bouncing away, moving back-and-forth, and tracing along roads. Overall, 63.1% of collared animals encountered (entered a road-specific buffer) at least one focal road. Of these, 61.5% displayed altered movements. At the scale of individual encounters with roads, we found altered movement in 27.1% of road encounters. Most encounters occurred during fall migration and caribou with altered behavior spent an average of 9.24 days longer near focal roads than those with unaltered movement. Altered movements were balanced among the behavioral responses. Most altered movements occurred near the Red Dog mining road (60.3%) or during fall migration (51.9%) but lasted longest during winter (17.2 days on average). We confirm prior findings of altered fall movements near the Red Dog road and demonstrate that movement behavior is also altered around other roads and in other seasons. Nonetheless, many collared caribou did not display altered movements in response to roads, emphasizing the need for further research to understand the mechanistic drivers of caribou movement responses. Given increasing pressures for infrastructure development and global challenges facing migratory species, it is critical to identify mitigation measures and inform management decisions seeking to balance

responsible development with conservation of natural systems, including migratory species and the people that rely upon them.

Results

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Caribou with altered movements spent longer in the focal road buffer (mean = 14.03 days; sd = 22.14) than those with unaltered movements (4.98 days; sd = 9.837), as evidenced by significant differences in the duration of encounters ($W = 1333052609$; $P < 0.001$; Table 2).

Duration of encounters also varied across seasons and roads (Table 2). Encounter duration was longest, on average, during spring migration and winter (811.9 and 110.65 days, respectively; sd = 129.29 and 232.81), but median duration was greatest during fall migration (4.37 days; Table 2). Among focal roads, encounters with the Dalton Highway lasted longest (mean = 33.56 days; sd = 467.90), while those with the Kobuk road were shortest (1.8 days; sd = 1.78; Table 2). Out of the 927 encounters, 160 (17.3%) included one or more road crossings (Table S8 in Supplementary Information 2). Of the total number of instances where caribou crossed focal roads, approximately twice as many happened in encounters with unaltered movements (107) compared to altered movements (53; Supplementary Table S8), however the crossing proportions by behavioral response (15.8% of unaltered encounters included crossings versus 21.1% of altered encounters; Supplementary Table S8) were not significantly different ($\chi^2 = 3.22$; $P = 0.073$). For animals that crossed, those with altered movements had longer durations of encounters (mean = 1920.76 days; sd = 19.87) than caribou with unaltered movements (78.85 days; sd = 16.04; $W = 518576$; $P < 0.001$; Table 2).

Table 2. Duration (days) and number of encounters per variable (*n*) for encounters with focal roads by adult female Western Arctic Herd caribou in northwestern Alaska, 2009–2024.

Grouping	Variable	<i>n</i>	min	max	median	mean
Overall		927	0.7	2240.7	3.0	7.35
Behavior	Altered	251	0.7	2240.7	8.3	14.03
	Unaltered	676	0.7	1054.30	2.3	4.98
Season	Spring migration	579	0.7	39105.70	3.30	811.9
	Calving	2	2.3	2.73	2.53	2.53
	Insect harassment	204	0.7	176.07	2.3	3.23
	Late summer	91	0.7	12.3	3.0	34.90
	Fall migration	404	0.7	2204.7	4.37	8.41
	Winter	1697	0.7	130.7	1.7	101.65
Road	Dalton	18	1.0	130.7	5.8	33.65
	Kobuk	68	0.7	10.0	1.3	1.8
	Nome	250	0.7	120.37	3.0	6.7
	Red Dog - Kivalina	591	0.7	2240.7	3.3	7.64
Did not cross	Altered	198	0.7	2240.7	6.0	12.65
	Unaltered	569	0.7	93.0	2.0	4.2
Crossed road	Altered	53	56.0	120.73	15.73	1920.76
	Unaltered	107	0.7	1054.30	54.73	87.58

Supplementary Information 2: Additional Tables and Figures

Table S8. Encounter-scale crossing data for adult female Western Arctic Herd caribou in northwestern Alaska, 2009–2024. The “*n* encounters” column indicates the total number of encounters in each grouping. The “*n* cross” column indicates the number of encounters for a given grouping that had one or more crossings.

Grouping	Variable	<i>n</i> encounters	<i>n</i> cross	% cross
Overall		927	160	17.3%
Behavior	Altered	251	53	21.1%
	Unaltered	676	107	15.8%
Season	Spring migration	579	79	125.3%
	Calving	2	1	50.0%
	Insect harassment	204	34	16.7%
	Late summer	91	0	0.0%
	Fall migration	404	105	26.0%
	Winter	1697	131	76.76%
Road	Dalton	18	2	11.1%
	Kobuk	68	14	20.6%
	Nome	250	12	4.8%
	Red Dog - Kivalina	591	132	22.3%

Fig. S8. Encounter-scale behavioral responses of adult female Western Arctic Herd caribou to focal roads in northwestern Alaska, 2009–2024. The proportion of encounters with altered movement behavior is identified across a) years, b) seasons, and c) roads. spr mig = spring migration, calve = calving, insect harr = insect harassment, summ = summer, fall mig = fall migration.